

IDENTIFYING THE DIDACTIC POSSIBILITIES OF DEVELOPING A METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION FOR FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' READING LITERACY

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Abstract: Today, in the primary education system, the quality methodological preparation of future teachers is gaining particular importance. Specifically, developing reading literacy in primary grades is considered one of the most important directions of the pedagogical process. At this stage, teachers perform the task of forming students' fundamental knowledge, skills, and competencies, teaching them literacy, thinking, and independent reading. Therefore, it is essential to properly and effectively prepare teachers methodologically.

Keywords: development of the educational process, training personnel who can meet modern and international requirements, providing broad opportunities for independent learning, facing several related problems. Furthermore, current innovations are leading to the emergence of new directions for improving methodological support for future primary school teachers.

The basis for improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for developing students' reading literacy includes communities, groups, and individual forms of training. New forms and methods of teaching in higher education are being developed. The main factors for enhancing the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers include modern educational content, laws, principles, methods, tools, teaching forms, and control methods.

Teaching and education is a purposeful systematic process equipped with knowledge and skills. Education is considered the result of teaching. Applying modern methods in the educational process ensures the development of independent thinking, analysis, drawing necessary conclusions, freely expressing opinions, defending them reasonably, active communication, discussions, and debates among learners. These methods increase activity among learners, develop personal qualities, activate assimilation, and improve the effectiveness of lessons by applying interactive methods.

In recent years, emphasis has been placed on the use of modern teaching methods to organize education based on world standards. The direct application of modern methods in the educational process increases the overall efficiency of teaching. It can be seen from international experience that interactive methods are increasingly used and their effectiveness and quality indicators are improving [4]. Applying modern teaching methods in the educational process helps future primary school teachers not only improve their methodological preparation for developing students' reading literacy but also foster independent learning and thinking, independently analyze existing problems, clearly express and defend their opinions based on concrete data, steadily increase the activity of knowledge assimilation, summarize solutions, develop discussion skills, and effectively use acquired knowledge in pedagogical activities [10]. The primary education concept emphasizes the following: the primary education process must be organized primarily on the principle of

humanism. Because the educational policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is distinguished by its humane nature. This policy is mainly directed toward universal human values.

The primary education process, based on the humanism principle, should ensure the free development of students. With the global processes of integration and globalization, the content and essence of education are changing. Therefore, primary school teachers face an extremely important task — forming independent thinking individuals with self-awareness potential and a new intellectual level. Such students must be capable of theoretical thinking, creative activity, and independently managing their behavior and actions. In this regard, improving the professional training of future primary school teachers is especially urgent. Because the process of purposeful teaching and upbringing of primary school students begins specifically with primary school teachers[5].

After adopting the new edition of the “Law on Education” of the Republic of Uzbekistan, comprehensive positive changes have been implemented in our country’s education system, especially in primary education.

Based on the national curriculum, the content of general secondary education, including primary education, has been updated; the state standard for primary education and new curricula have been developed and gradually introduced into the educational process. A new generation of textbooks has been created based on the state education standard and national curriculum. Students are now fully provided with modern textbooks.

Today, student-centered approaches are replacing traditional teaching. From this perspective, it is urgent to regularly monitor students’ acquired knowledge, skills, and competencies; timely fill gaps in knowledge; create conditions for the intellectual potential of talented students to develop steadily; encourage cooperation with adults; protect and strengthen students’ health; enrich pedagogical approaches and experience; develop extracurricular pedagogical activity plans; consistently use modern pedagogical technologies and achievements of pedagogical science in the educational process, including integrating information and communication technology elements; establish cooperation between teachers and parents; retrain and continuously improve the qualifications of primary school teachers using modern methods.

Educational regulatory documents also pay special attention to the preparation of teachers for primary grades.

Among the shortcomings hindering the preparation of creative individuals are not only the lack of continuity in teaching psychological-pedagogical subjects but also the following:

- insufficient development of interdisciplinary connections between methodological, specialized, and humanitarian subjects;

- unresolved issues of determining the optimal ratio of education forms related to labor activities, with disproportion still noticeable between lectures, seminars, laboratories, practical training, and school internships;

- unresolved issues of the optimal ratio between the theoretical and practical components of professional training;

- insufficient attention to professional-personal development and introduction of technological innovations (such as integration of knowledge and skills, use of information technologies) in the educational process of higher education institutions;

almost no practice of studying interdisciplinary subjects that allow for the development of social, managerial, and information-communication competencies;

insufficient attention to integrative aspects of training primary school teachers and others in higher education curricula.

No matter how deep theoretical training is or how many hours and subjects are allocated, it alone cannot form the scientific basis of future pedagogical activity.

Students educated by traditional teaching methodology mostly listen, see, memorize, repeat, and recite but rarely think critically. They seldom engage in problem posing, hypothesis formulation and solution, or establishing communication and relationships[6]. Therefore, traditional methods are not exemplary for using active teaching forms and methods when working with primary school students.

The methodological training practice shows a tendency toward performing already developed actions (analysis, evaluation, synthesis). Students rarely design the educational process independently or compose components related to specific learning situations. Moreover, more attention is paid to content work.

Contradictions in students' methodological preparation include:

between mastering existing methodological experience and ensuring and improving developmental education;

between the pedagogical higher education courses “Native language - reading literacy and its teaching methodology” and the primary school course “Reading literacy,” reflecting contradictions between student-centered education and primary teaching methods, as well as between competency-based approaches in curricula and methodological training in higher education for primary education, etc.

New priorities are emerging in improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers to develop students’ reading literacy. Along with studying the scientific foundations, applying acquired knowledge to solve practical problems, eliminating various problematic situations, and mastering methods and methodologies of learning.

Didactic materials play a crucial role in the formation of students' knowledge, skills, competencies, and qualifications during the educational process. The effectiveness of education largely depends on the proper selection and efficient use of didactic materials. As the modern education system embraces innovative changes, the extent to which didactic materials are effectively utilized significantly influences the overall outcomes of both teachers and students.

Didactic materials serve as tools that support the learning process and facilitate students' acquisition of knowledge[9]. These materials can take various forms, including visual, audiovisual, interactive, printed, and electronic formats. Such resources help make the learning process more engaging and comprehensible while also reinforcing students’ understanding[3].

Images, diagrams, tables, and graphs assist students in grasping subject content more effectively by simplifying complex information into logical and accessible formats. For example, illustrating words or sentences with pictures for primary school pupils enhances their comprehension abilities.

Videos, audio recordings, and interactive lessons capture students' attention and enable more effective transmission of information. Audiovisual tools support teachers in explaining complex topics in a clearer and more accessible way.

Textbooks, study guides, and other printed resources are also considered didactic materials. These serve as primary sources of information for students and contribute to the development of their independent reading and analytical skills.

Didactic materials assist in conveying complex concepts in a simplified and understandable manner. The more clearly and engagingly a teacher presents a topic, the more effectively students can comprehend and internalize the material. For instance, graphs and diagrams help represent intricate mathematical or scientific data in an easier-to-understand format.

Engaging students in the lesson is greatly facilitated by the use of didactic materials. Visual and audiovisual tools spark interest in students and enhance their motivation towards both the lesson and the subject matter. For example, captivating videos or interactive games increase students' participation and encourage active learning.

To effectively consolidate students' knowledge, didactic materials must be diverse and purposeful. Through their use, students are able to gain deeper understanding and learn how to apply their knowledge in practice. For instance, during practical sessions or with the aid of interactive textbooks, students not only learn but also reinforce their understanding of the subject matter.

Didactic resources foster students' independent learning and analytical skills. They motivate learners to search for new information and cultivate a desire for self-directed study. For example, electronic textbooks and interactive guides encourage autonomous exploration and learning[2].

Moreover, didactic materials function as a means of effective communication between teachers and students. Learners may consult these resources to find answers to their questions and engage in dialogue with instructors, thereby strengthening collaboration and enhancing educational outcomes.

When selecting didactic materials, educators should consider students' abilities and individual needs. This approach increases learners' interest in the learning process and contributes to their academic success[8].

Modern technologies enable a more effective organization of the educational process. For instance, digital whiteboards, educational software, and interactive games promote active student engagement in classroom activities.

Integrating various types of didactic tools within the teaching process makes learning more comprehensive and engaging. Combining visual, audio, and printed materials allows educators to cater to diverse learning styles and abilities.

Didactic materials contribute not only to the development of theoretical knowledge but also to the acquisition of practical skills. For example, through hands-on or seminar sessions, students are able to master topics more thoroughly. The "collaborative learning" approach fosters students' ability to work together and makes a significant contribution to teaching reading literacy. In this method, students engage in group activities, read and analyze texts related to the topic collaboratively [1].

Students are divided into small groups to study the topic together, comprehend the material, and exchange ideas. This approach enhances communication among students and increases their opportunities to learn from one another.

Students are also encouraged to express various ideas using the “brainstorming” technique in order to solve problems or find answers to questions. This method is considered effective in developing their creative thinking skills.

In conclusion, didactic materials are essential tools for enhancing the effectiveness of the educational process. They play a fundamental role in making learning logical and engaging, fostering students’ independent learning abilities, and ensuring a dynamic and interactive learning environment. Properly selected and implemented didactic resources significantly contribute to improving students’ understanding of academic content and achieving educational success.

Independent learning is an effective approach for students to master a given topic. Within this approach, students are given the opportunity to analyze, comprehend, and express their opinions on the tasks related to the subject during the learning process. The instructor, while providing guidance, also creates conditions for students to develop independent thinking skills.

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